

Environmental qualities of public playgrounds from the user perspective: A Scoping Review Protocol

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this scoping review is to understand the extent and type of evidence in relation to how environmental qualities influence the outdoor play experience of children with and without disabilities and their families and how play value is understood from the user perspective.

Introduction: Playgrounds are considered important places for children with and without disabilities and their family members. Children with disabilities encounter barriers on public playgrounds. A user perspective understanding on what and how environmental qualities on public playgrounds influences outdoor play of children with and without disabilities might give a better understanding of what needs to be considered when inclusive play is the goal.

Inclusion criteria: This scoping review will include published studies and grey literature concerning outdoor play on public playgrounds, investigating the user perspective on environmental qualities of children with and without disability and their family members.

Methods: This scoping review follows Arskey and O'Mally (2005) guidelines. Peer-review published articles, as well as grey literature, will be included. Searches are conducted between July 2021 to October 2021. Search limitations are set to literature in English and German language. Grey literature will include unpublished research.

Introduction

Public playgrounds are defined as outdoor environments which contain play opportunities built for the purpose of play, located in public parks or schools usually is available to the general public (Burke, 2012). Studies from different countries such as Korea, Ireland, Switzerland, or Sweden found that playgrounds are considered by children with and without disabilities as a significant environment in their life (Lynch et al., 2020; Min & Lee, 2006; Moore & Lynch, 2015; Prellwitz & Skär, 2007; Wenger et al., 2020) and encompass psychological, symbolic and behavioral meaning to children (Min & Lee, 2006). Several papers showed that children and families of various ages and abilities regularly visit playgrounds (Jansson, 2010; Little & Eager, 2010; Lynch et al., 2020; Nicholson et al., 2015). Playgrounds are built to offer children the possibilities to engage in outdoor play. Thus playgrounds are seen to be valuable environments and considered as important for children's social, physical, and emotional development (e.g. Ripat & Becker, 2012). It is known that children with disabilities participate less in outdoor play in the community and are more involved in home occupations (Bedell et al., 2013). Children with disabilities often do not have the possibilities to participate in outdoor play because of environmental barriers considering physical, social, or political barriers (e.g. Moore et al., 2020; Van Melik & Althuisen, 2020). Studies have emphasized that to overcome these barriers an understanding of the user perspective on public playgrounds is valuable (e.g. Dunn & Moore, 2005; Wenger et al., 2020). This is especially important when designing for play for children with diverse abilities and their families. Yet, playground providers do not have sufficient knowledge on providing outdoor play for children with and without disabilities and their families (Dunn & Moore, 2005; Lynch et al., 2020; Serman et al., 2019; Wenger et al., 2020). Previous scholar work describes that outdoor play for children with disabilities is experienced likewise to their peers, but they might pursue play differently according to their abilities and equally according to the environment which prevents or supports their play (Prellwitz & Skär, 2007; Wenger et al., 2020). Such common characteristics are the experience of fun and happiness, the importance of social interaction, the emphasis on the process rather than the outcome of play, the importance of mastery and encounter appropriate challenges as well the possibility to self-imitate and self-direct the play (Besio et al., 2016; Moore & Lynch, 2018; Nicholson et al., 2014; Prellwitz & Skär, 2007; Stephenson, 2002).

Play value

Several different definitions exist of play value. The term of play value has been described before in relation to playgrounds and is understood as the value for play that a playground provides (Woolley & Lowe, 2013). Play value could be looked at in physical environmental characteristics like spaces (e.g. location, landform, vegetation) and objects (e.g. loose materials, play components) as well as social environmental characteristics such as a playground for possibilities in engaging with other children social play (Woolley & Lowe, 2013). This definition understands play value by just looking at the environment without considering the user's perspective. A different definition encompasses more the experience of the user:

“The term ‘play value’ is used to describe the value an environment, object, or piece of equipment brings to children's experience of play. Something may be described as having high play value if children are able to play with it in many different ways, integrate it into their own play or use it to expand or elaborate on their own ideas and actions. Simple play things (e.g. sticks, balls, sand) and ‘classic toys or games often have high play value than complex and expansive toy or equipment” (Playright, 2016, p. 12).

Other definitions describe play value in a space or an object when it allows the child to experience play concerning the play characteristic earlier described in this protocol. Lynch, Moore and Edwards et al. (2018) defined play value more in terms of if a playground provides play for the individual user. These understanding from the user perspective defines play value to the opportunities in a playground for example the opportunities for challenge, risk, and fun (Lynch et al., 2018). The “play experiences that offer the most fun and that are most popular for the children are those that have highest play value” (Lynch et al., 2018 p.142). These different understandings of what play value is are still unclear and have yet to be defined.

Several other reviews on the topic have been conducted. Previous reviews looked at just the parents perspective of children with disabilities (Sterman et al., 2016), design features that are reported to be important for different disabilities (Fernelius & Christensen, 2017), investigated environmental design features such as accessibility and usability (Brown et al., 2021; Moore & Lynch, 2015) or reviewed evidence how Universal Design enhances inclusion and social participant (Moore et al., 2020). Other reviews have been investigating environmental qualities in the locale neighborhood playability but did not focus on public playgrounds and excluded children with disabilities (Gemmell et al., 2020). No review has been found investigating the literature by looking at the children with diverse abilities and their families and how the environmental qualities contribute to play value experience.

Review question

What is known about how environmental qualities of public playgrounds contribute to the user experience of outdoor play in children with and without disabilities?

The aim of this review is first, to summarize and compare the user’s experiences (children with and without disability and family/parents) to gain insight into what environmental qualities maximize the play value on public playgrounds for all children.

And second to produce new evidence from a synthesis of reviewed research articles and grey literature. This scoping review will seek to identify and develop themes within and across reviewed studies and grey literature by examining similarities and differences in what play value on public playgrounds means for diverse users. Such new knowledge is needed to understand what public playgrounds need to provide to facilitate play for children with diverse abilities and their families.

Keywords

Playground, play value, inclusive play, environment

Eligibility criteria

Participants

This scoping review will include studies and grey literature investigating children with and without disabilities (children with different abilities) and their family members.

Inclusion	Exclusion
Studies and grey literature that included children and youth with and without disabilities	Studies that <u>just</u> included children or adolescents without disability and/or older than 12 years

(including studies that investigated in both children with and without disability).	
Studies and grey literature that included parents, or other family members of children with and without disabilities (including studies that investigated in both parents and other family members of children with and without disability)	Studies that <u>just</u> included parents, or other family members of children or adolescents without disabilities and/or older than 12 years
Studies and grey literature that investigated in older populations retrospectively looking back to childhood	

Concept

This scoping review will investigate environmental qualities on public playgrounds.

Inclusion	Exclusion
Studies and grey literature that investigate in build and non-build environmental qualities of public playgrounds	
Studies and grey literature that investigates the user experience/user perspective of outdoor play on public playgrounds	Studies and grey literature that aims to investigate physical activity on public playgrounds.
Studies and grey literature that investigates in play value or playability of public playgrounds	Studies and grey literature that investigates safety standards

Context

This scoping review will search for published and unpublished studies looking at the context of public playgrounds.

Inclusion	Exclusion
Studies and grey literature investigate playgrounds open for public use	Studies that investigate private playgrounds – including playgrounds exclusively for schools
Studies and grey literature looking at environments built for the purpose of play (e.g. play spaces, playgrounds, natural playgrounds)	Studies looking at public spaces not built for the purpose of play
Studies and grey literature focusing on user perspective of play	
Studies and grey literature that look at user experience on school playgrounds, when playgrounds are used outside of school hours	Studies investigation in the teacher perspective
Studies and grey literature investigate in play experience mixed school and public playgrounds within one study	Studies and grey literature when play on playground is supervised through a teacher or other professions (e.g. play worker)

Studies and grey literature considering virtual environment offered in an outdoor environment will be considered	Studies and grey literature considering spaces meant or built for the purpose of play but offered virtually and indoor will be excluded.
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Types of Sources

This scoping review will consider both qualitative and quantitative study designs. Other published systematic reviews, as well as research reports published in peer review journals, will be included. In addition, grey literature including unpublished theses, research reports, and conference proceedings. Grey literature that will be considered are guidelines as well as policy documents.

Literature in English and German will be included as the authors speak these languages.

No limitations in the year of publications are set.

Methods

This scoping review will follow the stages identified by Arksey and O'Malley (2005). Levac et al. (2010) and guidelines from the Joanna Briggs Institute (Peters et al., 2020) are followed to ensure methodological rigor.

Search strategy

The three-step search strategy will aim to locate both published and unpublished studies. An initial search on Scopus helped to identify and map relevant papers on the topic. In this step abstracts, title and keywords have been scanned from several papers to generate search terms. All search terms could be found in table 1. The search string will be adopted to fit included databases.

In the second phase all found search terms are used to search the following databases:

- Scopus
- Web of Science
- Academic Search Complete
- Cinahl
- PsyINFO
- MEDLINE
- Avery Index to Architectural Periodicals.

The reason why several databases are needed is that the topic of interest considered an interprofessional topic including medical, educational, social sciences and architectural related sciences. Search strings used in the different databases in initial searches are displayed in table 2.

Table 1

Search terms

Concept	Search terms
playground	playground* OR playscap* OR playspac* OR "play spac*" OR "play area"
Environmental qualities	buil* OR design* OR provi* OR natur* OR outdoor OR inclusive
Population	Child* OR kid* OR caregiver* OR parent* OR mother* OR father* OR famil*

Table 2

Test searches with search string

Date	Database	Searchstring	Limit to	Hints
13.08.2021	PsyInfo through EBSCO	(playground* OR playscap* OR playspac* OR "play spac*" OR "play area*") AND AB (buil* OR design* OR provi* OR natur* OR outdoor * OR inclusive) AND AB (child* OR kid* OR caregiver* OR parent* OR mother* OR father* OR famil*)	Academic articles dissertations Abstract/Title/Subject Terms	552
13.08.2021	SCOPUS	TITLE-ABS-KEY (playground* OR playscap* OR playspac* OR "play spac*" OR "play area*") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (buil* OR design* OR provi* OR natur* OR outdoor OR inclusive) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (child* OR kid* OR caregiver* OR parent* OR mother* OR father* OR famil*)	Journal articles TITLE/ABSTRACT/KEYWORDS	1790

Grey literature search including unpublished research studies (e.g. doctoral or master theses) as well as research reports and conference proceedings. Several ways will be used to identify grey literature. For instance, databases for unpublished research such as EBSCO open Dissertations will be searched.

Second, the full-text analysis will identify key authors in the field. Home universities' websites (e.g. thesis databases or repositories of universities of key authors) and or research laboratory websites from key authors will be seared to find research reports or unpublished research. Listed conference contributions of key authors will be investigated through the university and/or research laboratory websites. Key authors will be contacted via email to ask if other studies on the topic are in process, if there are known unpublished research, or if they could name other key authors.

Third, included full-text studies and full-text grey literature reference lists will be seared. A hand search of key journals (e.g. Children and Youth Environments) will be hand searched to ensure no studies are missed.

Study/Source of Evidence selection

After the searches are completed, all identified citations will be collated and uploaded into COVIDENCE (*Covidence Systematic Review Software, 2021*) and duplicates will be removed.

The review incorporates three main rounds: Each study will then be screened by at least two independent reviewers for assessment against the inclusion criteria. All researchers in the project team will review the first 25 articles together to refine the inclusion criteria. The first round will be done by the main researcher (TM) guided by the research team. In this step title and abstract will be scanned to ensure the published study is within the context of public playgrounds. In the second round, two or more reviewers will independently review reminding titles and abstracts. Throughout this process, reviewers will meet and inclusion criteria will be revised through a group discussion. Articles will be rated with yes (include), no (exclude), and maybe (unsure if include). All papers rated yes and maybe will be coming to the next step of review. A statement will be given on the agreement percentage (full and partial agreement).

In the third round of the review, included studies will be retrieved in full text for full-text review against the inclusion criteria by at least two or more independent reviewers. Again, inclusion criteria are refined through a group discussion. Reasons for exclusion of sources of evidence at full-text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer/s. A statement will be given on the agreement percentage (full and partial agreement). Results from included and excluded studies will be collected in a table and visualized in a flow chart.

Data Extraction

Data will be extracted in a data charting form. The charting form will contain the following information but is not limited to evolve post hoc again through discussions in the researcher team (Levac et al., 2010):

- Author
- year of publication
- professional background the study was looking at the conducted research
- the origin where the study was conducted
- the purpose of the study,
- study design (methodology and methods)
- participants characteristics (population under investigation)
- context
- key results related to the research question (environmental qualities are mentioned by and how is this environmental quality described to influence play experience in outdoor play on a public playground).

The charting process is iterative and will constantly be updated when the research team will come familiar with the included studies. The charting table will be tested by two authors with 5 studies. Then revision will be applied, and further charting will be done by the main researcher (TM). This process will be supported through discussions and verification (e.g. the supervisory team will verify the extracted data).

Data Analysis and Presentation

As recommended by Levac et al (2010) this step will be divided into two different steps (descriptive numerical analysis: e.g. population included, and qualitative thematic analysis of the results). The second step includes an inductive thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke (2006). Thematic analysis has been recommended in systematic reviews before (Levac et al., 2010; Thomas & Harden, 2008) and used in several other scoping review papers (e.g. Krieger et al., 2018; Moore et al., 2020). Thematic analysis is a sophisticated method for the synthesis of research that seeks to aggregate existing evidence and develop new knowledge by identifying patterns, similarities or differences, and disparity in themes across primary studies. A narrative summary will accompany the tabulated and/or charted results and will describe how the results relate to the review objective and question/s.

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Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this project.

References

Arksey, H., & O'Malley, L. (2005). Scoping studies: Towards a methodological framework.

International Journal of Social Research Methodology, 8(1), 19–32.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1364557032000119616>

Bedell, G., Coster, W., Law, M., Liljenquist, K., Kao, Y.-C., Teplicky, R., Anaby, D., & Khetani, M. A.

(2013). Community Participation, Supports, and Barriers of School-Age Children With and

Without Disabilities. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 94(2), 315–323.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2012.09.024>

Besio, S., Bulgarelli, D., & Stancheva-Popkostadinova, V. (Eds.). (2016). *Play development in children*

with disabilities. De Gruyter Open.

- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Brown, D. M. Y., Ross, T., Leo, J., Buliung, R. N., Shirazipour, C. H., Latimer-Cheung, A. E., & Arbour-Nicitopoulos, K. P. (2021). A Scoping Review of Evidence-Informed Recommendations for Designing Inclusive Playgrounds. *Frontiers in Rehabilitation Sciences*, 2, 664595. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fresc.2021.664595>
- Burke, J. (2012). ‘Some kids climb up; some kids climb down’: Culturally constructed play-worlds of children with impairments. *Disability & Society*, 27(7), 965–981. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2012.692026>
- Covidence systematic review software. (2021). Veritas Health Innovation. www.covidence.org
- Dunn, K., & Moore, M. (2005). Developing Accessible Play Space in the UK: A Social Model Approach. *Children, Youth and Environments*, 15(1), 332–354.
- Fernelius, C. L., & Christensen, K. M. (2017). Systematic Review of Evidence-Based Practices for Inclusive Playground Design. *Children, Youth and Environments*, 27(3), 78. <https://doi.org/10.7721/chilyoutenvi.27.3.0078>
- Gemmell, E., Ramsden, R., Brauer, M., & Brussoni, M. (2020). *Influence of neighborhood built environments on the outdoor, free play of children, aged 0-6 years: A systematic, mixed studies review*. PROSPERO CRD42020173288. https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospERO/display_record.php?ID=CRD42020173288
- Jansson, M. (2010). Attractive playgrounds: Some factors affecting user interest and visiting patterns. *Landscape Research*, 35(1), 63–81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01426390903414950>
- Krieger, B., Piškur, B., Schulze, C., Jakobs, U., Beurskens, A., & Moser, A. (2018). Supporting and hindering environments for participation of adolescents diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder: A scoping review. *PLOS ONE*, 13(8), e0202071. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0202071>

- Levac, D., Colquhoun, H., & O'Brien, K. K. (2010). Scoping studies: Advancing the methodology. *Implementation Science, 5*(1), 69. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-5-69>
- Little, H., & Eager, D. (2010). Risk, challenge and safety: Implications for play quality and playground design. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal, 18*(4), 497–513. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2010.525949>
- Lynch, H., Moore, A., Edwards, C., & Horgan, L. (2018). *Community Parks and Playgrounds: Intergenerational Participation through Universal Design Final Report For The Centre for Excellence in Universal*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22422.60486>
- Lynch, H., Moore, A., Edwards, C., & Horgan, L. (2020). Advancing play participation for all: The challenge of addressing play diversity and inclusion in community parks and playgrounds. *British Journal of Occupational Therapy, 83*(2), 107–117. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0308022619881936>
- Min, B., & Lee, J. (2006). Children's neighborhood place as a psychological and behavioral domain. *Journal of Environmental Psychology, 26*(1), 51–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2006.04.003>
- Moore, A., & Lynch, H. (2015). Accessibility and usability of playground environments for children under 12: A scoping review. *Scandinavian Journal of Occupational Therapy, 22*(5), 331–344. <https://doi.org/10.3109/11038128.2015.1049549>
- Moore, A., & Lynch, H. (2018). Understanding a child's conceptualisation of well-being through an exploration of happiness: The centrality of play, people and place. *Journal of Occupational Science, 25*(1), 124–141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2017.1377105>
- Moore, A., Lynch, H., & Boyle, B. (2020). Can universal design support outdoor play, social participation, and inclusion in public playgrounds? A scoping review. *Disability and Rehabilitation, 1*–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2020.1858353>

- Nicholson, J., Kurnik, J., Jevgjovikj, M., & Ufoegbune, V. (2015). Deconstructing adults' and children's discourse on children's play: Listening to children's voices to destabilise deficit narratives. *Early Child Development and Care*, 185(10), 1569–1586.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2015.1011149>
- Nicholson, J., Shimpi, P. M., Kurnik, J., Carducci, C., & Jevgjovikj, M. (2014). Listening to children's perspectives on play across the lifespan: Children's right to inform adults' discussions of contemporary play. *International Journal of Play*, 3(2), 136–156.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/21594937.2014.937963>
- Peters, M., Godfrey, C., McInerney, P., Munn, Z., Trico, A., & Khalil, H. (2020). Chapter 11: Scoping Reviews. In E. Aromataris & Z. Munn (Eds.), *JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis*. JBI.
<https://doi.org/10.46658/JBIMES-20-12>
- Playright. (2016). *Inclusive play space guide*. <https://playright.org.hk/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/Playright-Inclusive-Play-Space-Guide.pdf>
- Prellwitz, M., & Skär, L. (2007). Usability of playgrounds for children with different abilities. *Occupational Therapy International*, 14(3), 144–155. <https://doi.org/10.1002/oti.230>
- Ripat, J., & Becker, P. (2012). Playground Usability: What Do Playground Users Say?: Playground Usability: What Do Playground Users Say? *Occupational Therapy International*, 19(3), 144–153. <https://doi.org/10.1002/oti.1331>
- Stephenson, A. (2002). Opening up the outdoors: Exploring the relationship between the indoor and outdoor environments of a centre. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 10(1), 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13502930285208821>
- Sterman, J., Naughton, G. A., Bundy, A. C., Froude, E., & Villeneuve, M. A. (2019). Planning for outdoor play: Government and family decision-making. *Scandinavian Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 26(7), 484–495. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11038128.2018.1447010>

Sterman, J., Naughton, G., Froude, E., Villeneuve, M., Beetham, K., Wyver, S., & Bundy, A. (2016).

Outdoor Play Decisions by Caregivers of Children with Disabilities: A Systematic Review of Qualitative Studies. *J Dev Phys Disabil*, 27.

Thomas, J., & Harden, A. (2008). Methods for the thematic synthesis of qualitative research in systematic reviews. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 8(1), 45.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-8-45>

Van Melik, R., & Althuisen, N. (2020). Inclusive Play Policies: Disabled Children And Their Access To Dutch Playgrounds. *Tijdschrift Voor Economische En Sociale Geografie*, 0(0), 1–14.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/tesg.12457>

Wenger, I., Schulze, C., Lundström, U., & Prellwitz, M. (2020). Children’s perceptions of playing on inclusive playgrounds: A qualitative study. *Scandinavian Journal of Occupational Therapy*,

28(2), 136–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11038128.2020.1810768>

Woolley, H., & Lowe, A. (2013). Exploring the Relationship between Design Approach and Play Value of Outdoor Play Spaces. *Landscape Research*, 38(1), 53–74.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01426397.2011.640432>